

ISSN 2709-3409 (Online)

JOURNAL OF TERTIARY AND INDUSTRIAL SCIENCES

A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF THE HIGHER TECHNICAL TEACHERS'
TRAINING COLLEGE, KUMBA

**VOLUME 4, NUMBER 2
JULY, 2024**

**PUBLISHER:
HIGHER TECHNICAL TEACHERS' TRAINING COLLEGE (HTTC)
UNIVERSITY OF BUEA**

P.O Box: 249 Buea Road, Kumba
Tel: (+237) 33354691 – Fax: (+237) 33354692
Email: editor@jtis-httcubuea.com
Website: <https://www.jtis-httcubuea.com>

EDITORIAL BOARD

Supervision:

Professor Ngomo Horace Manga
University of Buea

Editor-in-Chief:

Prof. Akume Daniel Akume, University of Buea, Cameroon

Managing Editor:

Dr. Negou Ernest, University of Buea, Cameroon

Associate Editors:

Prof. Ebune B. Joseph, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Defang Henry, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Lissouck Daniel, University of Buea, Cameroon

Advisory Editors:

Prof. Tabi Johannes Atemnkeng, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Lyonga N. Agnes Ngale, University of Buea, Cameroon

Members of the Editorial Board:

Prof. Yamb Belle Emmanuel, University of Douala, Cameroon

Ambe J. Njoh, Ph.D., Professor of Environmental Science & Policy, School of Geosciences, University of South Florida, USA

Prof. John Akande, Bowen University, Nigeria

Prof. Talla Pierre Kisito, University of Dschang, Cameroon

Prof. Rosemary Shafack, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Njimanted Godfrey Forgha, University of Bamenda, Cameroon

Prof. Nzalie Joseph, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Mouange Ruben, IUT University of Ngaoundere, Cameroon

Prof. Boum Alexander, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Patrick Wanyu Kongnyuy, University of Bamenda, Cameroon

Prof. Tchuen Ghyslain, IUT Badjoun, University of Dschang, Cameroon

Prof. Rose Frii-Manyi Anjoh, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Foadieng Emmanuel, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Tchinda Rene, IUT Badjoun, University of Dschang, Cameroon

Prof. Tabi Pascal Tabot, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Katte Valentine, University of Bamenda, Cameroon

Prof. Zinkeng Martina, University of Buea, Cameroon

Prof. Obama Belinga Christian Theophile, University of Ebolowa, Cameroon

ISSN 2709-3409 (Online)

Prof. Nkongho Anyi Joseph, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Cordelia Givechek Kometa, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Ngouateu Wouagfack Paiguy, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Tchakoutio Alain, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Morfaw Bertrand, University of Buea, Cameroon
Prof. Tamba Gaston, IUT University, Douala, Cameroon
Prof. Koumi Simon, ENS, Ebolowa, University of Yaounde I
Prof. Ajongakoh Raymond, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Ntabe Eric, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Abanda Henry Fonbiyen, Oxford Brookes University, UK
Dr. Luis Alberto Torrez Cruz, University of Witwatersrand, South Africa
Dr. Aloyem Kaze Claude Vidal, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Mfombep Priscilla Mebong, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Asoba Gillian, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Bahel Benjamin, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Agbortoko Ayuk Nkem, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Mouzong Pemi, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Orock Fidelis Tanyi, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Wanie Clarkson Mvo, University of Bamenda, Cameroon
Dr. Molombe Jeff Mbella, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Emmanuel Tata Sunjo, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Ndi Roland Akoh, University of Yaounde I, Cameroon
Dr. Kinfack Juetsa Aubin, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Kamda Silapeux Aristide, University of Buea, Cameroon
Dr. Roland Ndah Njoh, University of Buea, Cameroon

Table of Contents

NUMERISATION	1
NONLINEAR NUMERICAL APPROXIMATIONS OF TRANSPORT COEFFICIENTS AND PHENOMENOLOGICAL COEFFICIENTS GOVERNING THE COCOA DRYING PROCESS	2
AGRICULTURE	21
IMPACT OF MECHANIZATION ON AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY IN CAMEROON	22
GEOGRAPHY	48
EVALUATION OF URBAN DEVELOPMENT IN NKONGSAMBA, LITTORAL REGION, CAMEROON: CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS FOR SUSTAINABILITY	49
LE MONT NGAOUNDERE, UN GEOMORPHOSITE D'ESCALADE, PEPITE DU DEVELOPPEMENT DU TOURISME D'OBSERVATION DANS LA VINA ADAMAOUA (CAMEROUN)	72
FOSTERING REGIONAL GROWTH AND DEVELOPMENT THROUGH A DECENTRALISED PERSPECTIVE: LESSONS FROM KUMBA AND TIKO MUNICIPALITIES, SOUTH WEST REGION, CAMEROON	90
MANAGEMENT	113
WORKFORCE DIVERSITY: A CONTRIBUTION TO EMPLOYEES' PERFORMANCE IN STATE UNIVERSITIES IN CAMEROON	114
SCIENCE OF EDUCATION	131
THE EFFECT OF AUTOMATIC PROMOTION ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTELLECTUAL SKILLS BY FORM ONE STUDENTS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN THE KUMBA II MUNICIPALITY, MEME DIVISION, SOUTH WEST REGION OF CAMEROON	132
LA RESPONSABILITE DES MEMBRES DE LA COMMUNAUTE EDUCATIVE DANS LA PRODUCTION DES VIOLENCES EN MILIEU SCOLAIRE AU CAMEROUN: CAS DES PARENTS D'ELEVES DEVIANTS DES COLLEGES PRIVES CEBER ET IPS A YAOUNDE 4	150
LA DIFFAMATION, LES DÉCLARATIONS MENSONGÈRES, L'OUTRAGE ET LES FAUSSES NOUVELLES DIRIGÉS À L'ENDROIT DES ENSEIGNANTS COMME PRATIQUES SOCIOÉDUCATIVES DÉVIANTES	171
HISTORY	193
TRANSFORMATION OF BAKUNDU-LAND UNDER BRITISH COLONIAL ADMINISTRATION, 1922 - 1960	194

GEOGRAPHY

**EVALUATION OF URBAN DEVELOPMENT IN NKONGSAMBA, LITTORAL
REGION, CAMEROON: CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS FOR
SUSTAINABILITY**

By

Agbortoko Manyigbe Ayuk Nkem & Fombe Lawrence Fon

University of Buea

Contact email: agbor.ayuknkem@gmail.com

Submission Date: 17/04/2024

Acceptation Date: 19/06/2024

Abstract

This research study on the evaluation of urban development in Nkongsamba is based on a historical assessment of the developmental changes that have been manifested from 1950 to present. It begins with an assessment of the major activities that made the Town a growth pole and ends with a detailed examination of the problems impeding development. The study also takes into consideration the factors that led to the growth and decline of the Town's economy. The study adopted a survey research method with the use of both primary and secondary sources of data. Direct interviews were made with some actors involved in the coffee sector as well as those once involved in the sector to understand the trends of activities and its relation to the growth and development of the Town. Secondary sources included archival materials on the growth and development of the Town. Based on cartographic information on location and layout, base maps were collected from the Delegation of Lands and survey and the Municipal council. From the data collected, it was realised that, the emergence of the coffee trade in Nkongsamba and the sustained drop in the coffee prices at the world market had an intricate link to the growth and decline of the economy of Nkongsamba. Other factors like the collapse of the railway and the relocation of banks to other growing settlements, as well as retail trades played a contributory role in the decline of the Town. Today, Nkongsamba is seen as a pale reflection of the urban settlement it used to be with out-migration of the teeming population to other growth poles like Douala, Melong and Bafoussam. A proper planning approach through rehabilitation and reconstruction of housing, roads and the revitalization of businesses is a way forward which could bring about growth and development to the once prosperous Nkongsamba.

Keywords: Urban Development, Nkongsamba, Challenges and Prospects, Sustainability, Littoral Region

1 Introduction

Since their earliest origins, urban settlements have been centres of education, religion, commerce, record keeping, communication, and political power (Nawagamuwa, et al., 2003). As cradles of civilization, urban areas have influenced culture, and society far beyond their proportion of the total population. The history of urbanization according to Drakakis-Smith, (2000), indicates that the first cities on earth occurred in the region of Mesopotamia (now Iraq), around 3500 B.C, among other parts like the Nile Valley (Egypt), the Industrial Valley (Pakistan), as well as the Hoang-Ho Valley (China). This shows that, only societies based on redistribution where surplus over consumption can be appropriate by a particular group that urbanization is possible. However, the evolution of urbanization over human historical time from the first cities through the medieval periods to the modern times, has demonstrated a wide range of urban societies with fundamental differences between them.

It can be argued that urban development is a function of the introduction of Western industrialization, capitalism, and Imperialism in Third world societies which were and still are predominantly rural communities (Gilbert, et al., 1981). The impact of European imperialism and expansion from the 16th century onwards transformed urban morphology and structure in developing countries (Fombe, 2005). In the words of Hoselitz (1953), "The cities of contemporary underdeveloped countries are hybrid institutions formed in part as a response of the indigenously developing division of the social labour and in part as a response to the impact made upon less advanced countries by their integration into the world economy. This of course emphasizes this process on European capitalism of penetration and its effect on the urbanization of developing countries. In Africa, most of the urban development today is reflections of the European creation of Towns during the colonial period and to the trading relationship with Europe. Some of these urban centres among others include Yaoundé, Nairobi, Kinshasa, and Dakar. Most of these cities have now become primate cities in their different countries (Mabogunje, 1986).

In Cameroon, urbanization has been increasing steadily. According to the World Bank (2003), the urban population moved from 30% in 1987 to 44% in 2000, with the majority of the population living in the major Towns of Yaoundé and Douala. Presently, over 47% of the country's population live in urban areas according to the 2005 census. These Towns including others like Limbe and Nkongsamba were created by colonial masters in order to ease administration and ease of evacuating agricultural products and slaves through the ports to the western world (Nkongsamba Council Report, 1970). A Town like Nkongsamba developed during the colonial period to transport raw agricultural products to and from the hinterlands and gained much prominence as a terminus of the railroad from Douala. Most of these colonial cities today have become predominant in terms of growth and influence while others are just a mere relic of what they used to be during the colonial period. Nonetheless, most of these Towns still play the role of major urban centres and thus attract population from the surrounding suburbs. Unfortunately, some of the developmental aspects to foster growth as well as reviving the economy of these Towns have had little impact on their growth and development.

Nkongsamba, a major colonial Town in the Littoral Region of Cameroon whose growth was influenced by the French Agricultural Policy of intensive exploitation contributed to the Town's growth in the 20th century (Neba, 1999). Between 1975 and 1990, Nkongsamba was the 3rd city of Cameroon after Douala and Yaoundé in population size. Its vibrant and burgeoning agriculture churned out coffee, bananas and other tropical fruits for the export market while the rest of the country had a sustained supply of corn, sweet potatoes, cassava, plantains and other staples through Nkongsamba. As a result these natural endowments and dynamic population, the Mungo Division developed into a vibrant hub for education with schools emanating all over, and also championed by religious organizations and other local elites. It was the railway terminus from Douala, which performed the role as the break-of-bulk point to the "grand North" with road connections to Bamenda (north), Bafoussam (northeast), Douala (southeast), and Buea (southwest). Large oil palm, banana, and coffee plantations in the area made Nkongsamba a commercial centre with the railway line playing a critical economic role in facilitating the shipment of agricultural products. Coffee and tobacco from the north were shipped by rail to Douala for exportation. The Town had a food-processing plant, a teacher-training school, and a saw mill. With all these attributes, the Town was forced to attract a large number of people in the past. It was at this period that a local notary developed the Socka Bongue Institute, a classical, vocational and technical education institution that was designed to project the development efforts in Nkongsamba and the Mungo into the future.

In the mid-1970s and 1980s however, the Town began to decline in functions as a major urban centre, mainly as a result of the drop in the international coffee market price that made the once lucrative agricultural sector of the Town's economy to collapse. As pointed out by Breeze (1972), any city whose dwellers are based on a particular agricultural practice, will experience a consequent fall in its economy in cases of decline in prices of that produce. He further argued that, such population will experience a drop in standards of living, a reduction of its per capita income, among others, as evident in Nkongsamba. Also, the poor management of the coffee plantations and processing mills by the natives of Nkongsamba after the departure of the colonial masters, contributed to the fall of the coffee business. More so, the Town slid into economic decline with the closure of the last 50 km segment of the railway line from Mbanga in 1994. This according to the Socka Bongue Institute (1996), more than 30 people lost their jobs. These included farmers who used the railway as the main and cheaper means to transport their produce. It became expensive to use road transport. Thus, there was an increase in total expenditure accompanied by a decrease in overall profit and price of agricultural products. The Town's charming art deco railway station remains, but has been converted to a dormitory/business structures with liquor sales, Guinness retail stores and other craft workshops. Also, the innovation of the road link between Bafoussam and Douala which is more competitive as it is faster and flexible than the railway system, contributed to the collapse of the railway line. Furthermore, the old railway structures were not able to support the transportation of very bulky products, and therefore needed a change of the tract for a more resistant and reliable one. But, the collapse of the coffee economy as well as the construction of the Douala-Bafoussam road transport, led to the decline in the

activities of the railway services. Thus, the defunct “Regifercam” instead transferred resources to Douala for the renovation of the railway from Douala to Ngaoundere. This helped in the collapse of the railway line to Nkongsamba and its eventual closure.

In view of the above it can be understood that the Town of Nkongsamba, under Cameroon’s ranking of urban centres within the early 1970s, was classified as the third after Douala and Yaoundé. Today, with its declining socio-economic condition, it can be classified as a declining urban centre not capable of playing the vibrant relay role and development of the rich agricultural hinterland as exemplified by Rostow’s Model of 1960. The rapid rural exodus into Douala and other coastal cities by the youthful population of the vast agricultural hinterland of the Mungo is the outcome of Nkongsamba’s effete economy. Also, given the fact that this Town lost its influence as a major distribution centre, it has to some extent reduced its sphere of influence leading to a reduction in its interaction with other surrounding settlements. This may eventually lead to a state of “isolation”, which goes contrary to the expectations of Goal 11 of the Sustainable Development Goals.

The Rostow Model

This Model was put forward by W.W. Rostow in 1960 following a study of 15 countries, mainly in Europe. He suggested that all countries had the potential to break the cycle of poverty and to develop through five linear stages as seen in Figure 1. This study pays more interest in Stage 3, which constitute the Take-off. This stage can be described as a “Great watershed” in the life of a society. Manufacturing industries grow rapidly. Airports, roads and railways are built. Political and social adjustments are necessary to adapt to the new way of life. Growth is usually limited to one or two parts of the country (growth poles) and to one or two industries (magnets). Numbers in agriculture decline. Investment increases to 10-15% of GDP, or capital is borrowed from wealthier nations.

Fig 1: Rostow’s Five-Stage Development Model of Economic Growth
 Source: Potter et al. (2004)

As deduced from the characteristics of Stage 3, the colonial masters constructed roads and railway lines during the 1960s, linking other Towns like Yaoundé and Douala passing through Nkongsamba for the purpose of transporting goods from other surrounding regions, including Nkongsamba and environs, to the port of Douala for shipment. Growth was concentrated in the two major Towns of Yaoundé (the present day nation's Capital) and Douala (the present day economic capital) as growth poles which can be evident in the take-off stage of the model. The main source of income in the agricultural sector came from foreign investors and colonial masters whose sole aim was to transport the finished products to their home countries. This ties with the idea from the model, which explains that investment capital was borrowed from colonial countries among which includes France and Greece in order to boost productivity and growth. Also, the growth and development of the agro-industry was evident with mechanization in the form of processing machines, use of fertilizers, pesticides and other sophisticated equipment to improve on output. Investment was bound to increase as other services came up. An example was the packaging firm that produced plastics, the transportation company that helped in the transportation of finished products to the port of Douala for shipment, as well as other businesses to cater for the needs of the growing population.

Considering the above, it was evident for a drive to the next stage since the entire layout was structured to enhance growth of the Town. Nonetheless, it should be noted that, most of what made the Town to gain prominence was its agricultural potential. It should also be noted that, most of these agricultural firms were owned and managed by foreign investors, since the local indigenes lacked enough capital and expertise to carry out such heavy investments. However, the affluent few who were able to buy some of the firms on departure of the colonial masters, suffered the problem of a sustained drop in the price of the basic agricultural product (coffee) that sustained the economy of the Town. Thus, the Town was bound to decline in activity by losing its influence and status as a major growth pole in its region. The present state of Nkongsamba places it in the second stage of the Rostow's curve as most of the indicators within the take-off stage like the rapid growth of manufacturing industries, airports, roads and railways are no more being used as they are all facing degradation. Infrastructures like the manufacturing industries and the railway are no more in existence with the economy becoming more of subsistence than commercial as described in the first stage of the model thus, exhibiting a negative progression of the Town back to stage two of the Rostow's curve.

Given such a situation, it will be worth nothing that, for a Town to develop from stage one to stage three of the Rostow's development model and falls back to stage two, gives an indication of a lagging region which calls for concern both from planners and the government in order to revitalise the Town to its former status as well as understanding other growth potentials of the urban centre. This study therefore seeks to examine the development changes of Nkongsamba as well as prospects for growth based on its natural resource base.

2 Materials and Methods

Area of Study

Location

Nkongsamba is the administrative centre of the Mungo Division in the Littoral Region situated at $4^{\circ}90'$ of the northern latitude and $9^{\circ}80'$ of the eastern longitude. With its role as a rich agricultural region, its main road network gave it an important position during its glory years in the country's economy. The Town is well connected to other big Towns in Cameroon like Douala (about 145Km), Yaoundé (420Km), Bafoussam (115Km), Ngaoundere (820Km) and Garoua (about 1130Km). The location of the Town in the Littoral Region of Cameroon is presented in Map 1 and Map 2 illustrates the layout of Nkongsamba.

Map 1: Location of Nkongsamba in the Littoral Region

Source: Adapted from the Department of Surveys, Littoral Region, (2000)

Map 2: Layout of Nkongsamba showing the Three Administrative Divisions

Source: Adapted from Pierre Sime, (2007)

Research Methodology

In order to achieve the objective of this study, a survey research method was adopted. Both primary and secondary sources of data were collected and analysed. The primary sources included base maps, some coffee farmers, former railway workers, natives of the Nkongsamba municipality, Delegate of Urban Development and Housing, the Town Planning Delegation, the Mayors of the municipal councils, and taxi drivers. With respect to the secondary sources, both published and unpublished data were collected. Areas of focus were the Socka Bongue Institute, the Divisional Delegation of Urban Development and Housing, the Nkongsamba Municipal Councils, The archives of the Senior Divisional Officer for Nkongsamba, The National Archives of Buea and Douala, Internet service, and documentation in the Libraries of both the Universities of Buea and Douala were consulted.

Primary source material constitutes the original source of knowledge for the researcher from intuition and field observation. There was also the collection of data by field interviewing of specific authorities concerned with the study. The administration of the questionnaire in the field was done using systematic sampling technique especially in the sectors of the coffee farmers and Natives of Nkongsamba. The distribution of the questionnaires was aided by two field assistants in order for the researcher to cover the targeted scope of study. This technique was preferred since it reduced time, was less biased/costly, and also enabled at least 85% of the matrix to be sampled. Nonetheless,

the random sampling technique was also used in sampling the coffee farmers since there were many farmers to be interviewed and also to reduce bias, cost, and time. Areas covered included quarters like Mbaressountou (Rails, Aviation, Mosquée, Carrière, and Stade), Eboum 1, Eboum-mbeng, Mouam-Mbo'o, Eboum-Dja, Lele, Mouandja, Ndogmoa-Mbeng, Longko'o and Pastorale (Ekol-Mbeng), since they constituted about 80 percent of the population which comprised the farmers, former railway workers and non-farmers.

Based on the different neighbourhoods and respondents' category, questionnaires were administered to former railway workers to understand the state, function, causes and problems that led to the closure of the railway line from Mbanga to Nkongsamba. They were also questioned on some of the challenges faced as a result of closure of the railway. Also, coffee farmers were sampled to get information about the trend of coffee production, the fluctuation of the market prices, its role on the economy of the Town as well as its effect on employment levels in the Town. Some difficulties faced by this sector were also examined. It should be noted that at least 80% of the economy of Nkongsamba depended on agriculture (most especially, coffee). Thus, a majority of the questionnaires were shared among coffee farmers as agriculture played a major role in the Town's development trend.

The inhabitants, taxi drivers and bike riders were also interviewed in order to get information about the development trend of the Town; the problems the Town has been facing in terms of migration, employment and development. Information on the trend of employment and migration from the area was gotten in order to understand the major age group that migrated as well as reasons for the constant movement. More so, quarters like Eboum 1, Mbaressountou, Pastorale and Feroviere were of interest as these areas are noted during fieldwork for a good number of degraded streets, and roads.

Furthermore, council authorities, Divisional delegates of Urban Development and Housing, Town Planning, and Delegate of Lands and Surveys were all interviewed to understand some of the challenges they face in terms of development efforts in the Town. Some of the future prospects for development were also examined.

Data collected were analysed using two basic methods; the qualitative (descriptive) and the quantitative methods. From empirical data, tables were presented based on values considered at one decimal position to compare the rate of coffee production vis-à-vis the prices for specified years. From this, a trend in the coffee producing sector was constructed using a frequency curve. Tables were also constructed based on information from the indigenes in order to present graphs to interpret and explain the development trend of the Town. A cartographic analysis was also done to produce maps used in presentation of the study area.

3 Results

Growth and Development of the Agricultural (coffee) Economy

The French arrival in Cameroon after WWI, and the discovery of agricultural potentials within the country, saw the introduction of agricultural policies of intensive exploitation.

The growth of Nkongsamba was influenced largely by this French agricultural policy and contributed to the Town's growth in the 20th century (Ngwa, 1967). Before the creation of the Town in May 1923, coffee trade was already in existence with the main owners of the farms being foreigners from Greece, France, Portugal, and Spain. Though the economy was still at its early stages, it was already employing some of the inhabitants of the Town as well as others from neighbouring Towns and villages. Given the construction of the railway station by the French in 1917, the trade began to gain prominence, and the prices of coffee increased considerably in the world market. This helped to motivate farmers to produce more since there was a ready market.

From the 1950s onward, production increased (Fig. 2) as there was the introduction of fertilizers, pesticides, new farming techniques and use of machines in the farming and production process. Also, there was the construction of warehouses to store produce before shipment and semi-processing of these products in Nkongsamba before shipment overseas. This period of expansion in the agricultural sector evidently could be likened to the Industrial Revolution in the Western World. Figure 2 shows a trend in the production of Robusta coffee from 1972/73 to 1981/82. This increase in coffee production was also marked by an increase in demand and price from 1972/73 to 1981/82, a period of 10 years. The dwindling in production indicates periods of slump and booms respectively in the world market.

Fig. 2: Coffee production in tons and price in FCFA from 1972/73 to 1981/82
Source: Fieldwork (2010)

It can be deduced from Figure 2 that the increase in the production and price of the produce coincides with growth of the Town within this same period. It is also evident that the peak period of growth was between 1976/77 and 1980/81 where it levels out. During this period, despite the decrease in production from 1979 to 1980, the price within this same period continued to increase considerably. According to field data (2010), coffee

ISSN 2709-3409 (Online)

firms like Gortzounian Co., CACEP, and DAFCAM, employed between 300 and 400 workers with salary rates ranging from 100000 to 1 million FCFA. Another coffee firm known as Tzouvelous (the biggest of all the coffee firms), employed more than 2000 workers with salaries ranging from 80000 for labourers to 1.2-3 million for accountants and clerks. This improved on the per capita income and a general increase in the living standards of the population.

Growth and Development in Transport Services

The creation of the railway by the Germans in 1910 and the construction of the railway station by the French in 1917 formed the only means of transport into the Mungo Division and the Western Region of the country at that time. This line was used in the transportation of goods and services from the Douala Port through Nkongsamba to other surrounding regions. Due to the presence of the railway, the Town earned the title "break-of-bulk-point" into the northern Region. This was because goods leaving the Douala Port destined for the north had to pass through Nkongsamba before leaving for the north and vice versa for those transported to the port at Douala. More so, cattle, cotton, wheat and other products from the north and Chad, were transported to the Port of Douala through the railway line in Nkongsamba.

The railway also gained its prominence as it was used by the colonial masters in the transportation of agricultural produce for shipment through the Port of Douala to Europe and other demanding nations. More so, the railway was used in the transportation of farming equipment, merchants and other passengers from Douala, Mbanga, and Loum among others to different places. Thus, the railway was the major means of transportation as the roads were very bad and inaccessible especially in the rainy seasons and air transport was very expensive at the time.

As a result of the functions of the railway, other transportation companies began emerging in the Town. Good examples include major companies like La Chanas, Transport Co. Ltd among others which came up to transport goods from Nkongsamba to Chad, Central African Republic, Gabon and other neighbouring countries. The Town also enjoyed products of these countries from traders who travelled to the foreign zones. Some of the companies also helped in the transportation of goods from Nkongsamba to Yaoundé in order to help sustain its growing industries. Oral sources also indicate that wood from Belabo was transported to the seaport in Douala using the Nkongsamba rail line.

Furthermore, the colonial masters constructed roads and streets within the Town to help ease movements for administrative surveys and from the centre of the Town to their firms located within the outskirts. By so doing, these roads played a role in connecting Douala, Bafoussam, Dschang and those Towns located in the north since they used the road within the Town as the main passage. Thus, this road was constantly maintained by the colonial masters in order to continue providing the functions they were intended for.

Growth and development of other Infrastructures

As a result of the agricultural boom and the transport services, people were bound to migrate into the Town to seek employment and other lucrative opportunities that were

ISSN 2709-3409 (Online)

better than what they had back home. By so doing, there was a need to increase the infrastructures in order to cater for the growing population. The development of the road network ensured accessibility. This helped in the development of commercial centres and other businesses which came up to cater for the needs of the growing and demanding population. Companies like Tsekenis, Vlandis, Jalem, Herekigui, Continal, K.W. King, CFAO, SIRCO, PANAFRIC, Javeny, all developed to perform different functions among which include the production and selling of clothes (R.W. King), a glass company, construction companies, as well as companies involved in the production and sales of fertilizers and other agricultural equipment.

Also, there was the construction of filling stations which supplied fuel to the increasing population. Filling stations included SCDP, two Total sales point, two Texaco sales points, Mobil, and Agip were constructed in Nkongsamba. More so, sales of cars were also possible as there was a ready market in the Town. Companies like SOCADA (SCOA), CAMI TOYOTA, and RENAULT, were located in Nkongsamba between the 1960s and early 1980s. Furthermore, major banks and credit unions like the SGBC, SCB (now Société Commerciale de Banque Cameroun), BIAO, BICIC (now BICEC), the state Treasury, and the Provincial Finance control Office. All of these financial institutions worked towards the development of the economic sector of the Town and helped in international and national transactions for the farmers and foreigners resident in the area. Also, hotels were constructed to accommodate visitors and businessmen who were most often foreigners from Europe and other areas of the country. The best hotels (3 stars) by then included the hotel du Mungo, the guest house in Mbouroukou, as well as other small inns. It should also be noted that as a major growth centre in the Mungo division, and an administrative capital of that zone, there was enough security that gave the peaceful atmosphere for the different businesses to operate. This helped to attract investors from all parts of the country as well as Europe.

Decline in Socio-Economic Activities

Decline in the Coffee Economy

The coffee trade played a major role in the economy of Nkongsamba and was the main agricultural product that was exported from the Town during the 80s when the economy was vibrant. From 1982/83, the price of coffee began to drop in the world market. By 1984, a bag of coffee was sold at 5000 Frs CFA and a Kg for 100 Frs. This was far below the previous sales that fluctuated between 28000 and 40000 Frs CFA. This drop coincided with the collapse of the National Produce Marketing Board (NPMB), which was in the past helping the farmers to negotiate sales in the world market. Despite a continuous increase in the production of coffee from 1982/83 to 1994/95, the prices continued to drop as illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1: Coffee production and Price/Kg from 1982/83 to 1991/92

Year	1982/83	1983/84	1984/85	1985/86	1986/87
Production (Tons)	44,176	27,068	50,380	37,324	58,229
Price/Kg	180	150	100	80	90

Year	1987/88	1988/89	1989/90	1990/91	1991/92
Production (Tons)	34513	42947	36287	27895	26389
Price/Kg	120	120	140	150	200

Source: Delegation of Agriculture, Douala (1992)/ Statistic Bureau, MINEP, (1994)

The trend in prices and production of coffee within the decade of 1982-1992 is illustrated in Figure 3. The same figure epitomises the situation in which despite increase in coffee production, prices kept dropping. Also, the increase in production was a means to compensate the low price, thus, the larger the quantity, the more you earn. This encouraged the farmers to an extent to produce more despite the reduction in world market prices. However, the farmers by 1988/89 started reducing on the sizes of their coffee farms leading to a drop in production that was not accompanied with an increase in the price of the produce. In Figure 3, it is evidently clear that the prices of the produce were reducing and became severe between 1982/83 and 1985/86 wherein a Kg of coffee was sold below 100 Frs CFA. By 1986/87, the price started increasing though at lower rates. Presently, coffee prices vary between 180 Frs CFA and 240 Frs CFA/Kg.

In effect, the coffee economy today is not what it used to be in the 80s considering the fall in price/Kg from 640 Frs to 240 Frs CFA indicating a 68.7% drop. This discouraged farmers and obliged them to abandon their firms, machines, and warehouses (Plates 1 and 2), to look for other lucrative opportunities. More so, as a result of the low coffee prices, the farmers, those who used to contribute actively in the development of the Town through the construction of houses and demand for other commodities saw their purchasing power drop, thereby affecting the economy of the Town. Transportation companies, processing factories, retail car shops among others started relocating to other emerging settlements like Melong, Douala and Bafoussam.

Fig. 3: Trend of Coffee production and prices between 1982/83 to 1991/92

Source: Fieldwork (2010)

ISSN 2709-3409 (Online)

Furthermore, as a consequence of the low coffee prices, the farmers experienced a shift in the farming system from the traditional cash crop farming system to mixed cultivation in order to compensate for the drop in coffee business and as a means for livelihood. Crops like pineapples, maize, cassava, cocoyams and market gardening products like vegetables, carrots, beans among others were cultivated in large quantities for sale and home consumption.

*Plate 1: Abandoned coffee processing machines in a warehouse in Nkongsamba
Source: Field work, (November, 2009)*

*Plate 2: Abandoned Coffee warehouses in Nkongsamba
Source: Field work, (November 2009)*

More so, most of these coffee farms are between 50 and 60 years old, which needs replacement of the old coffee stems. However, since the business is no longer considered lucrative, the coffee stems are used as a good source of domestic fuel. The stems are being cut down in favour of other crops like maize, beans, carrots as well as vegetables. Some of these mixed farms are shown in Plate 3.

Plate 3: Coffee stems cut down in favour of other crops like maize and beans. Note the receding coffee plants in the background and food crops in the foreground.

Source: Field work (March, 2010)

Also, the planting of food crops within the widely spaced coffee plants was a system adapted by some farmers who were still dealing with the coffee trade but had to introduce their families in the cultivation of food crops within the coffee farms as seen in Plate 4.

Plate 4: Mixed farming system carried out by farmers in the study area

Source: Field work, (March, 2010)

As a consequence to this decline, many people lost their jobs, the per capita income of the population reduced drastically as well as the closure of related services attributed to the coffee trade. Added to these, most of the farmers now consider the coffee trade as a waste of time and prefer to turn to other lucrative farming activities among which are maize cultivation, pepper farming, market gardening products (vegetable and carrot cultivation), and beans which are presently being transported to Douala on Mondays and Thursday nights for sale. Recent fieldwork (2024) shows a marked increase in the

quantity of food produced being transported to major cities of the country including, Douala, Bafoussam, Buea and Limbe. Figure 4 provides information on the perception of farmers based on their reflection about the present condition of the coffee market.

Fig. 4: Farmers' view on the present condition of the coffee market
Source: Field work (2023)

Though coffee prices have been showing some slight increases from 2010 to 2023, the rates have been between 2,997 frs cfa to 3,805 frscfa. This is far below the original price for coffee which stood at between 28,000 frs to 40,000 frs during the glory days. Very few farmers are still in coffee farming. The reason some farmers considered the venture lucrative.

Slump in Commercial Activities

According to field Data (2010), the slump in commercial activities was closely linked to the decline in coffee trade within the mid-1980s and 1990. During this period, most of the coffee processing industries collapsed. Coffee farmers and workers related to the coffee trade that constituted a majority of the population in the Town experienced a decline in their purchasing power. This was intricately linked to retail trade which consequently experienced a decline as well.

In addition, the drop in coffee prices experienced the relocation of commercial banks like the S.G.B.C, SCB and BIAO, to other areas like Melong, Bafoussam and Douala. The main reason besides the falling profits from coffee trade was the problem of high taxes in Nkongsamba. It should be noted that, being a prosperous economy, tax systems in Nkongsamba were a reflection of the high standards comparative to other settlements. This therefore made most businesses to relocate to other areas as reduced profit and high tax can only lead to collapse in the business. Plate 5 illustrates some abandoned structures by former commercial banks in Nkongsamba.

Plate 5: Abandoned Structures by some Commercial Banks in Nkongsamba
Source: Field Work, (January, 2010)

From right to left of Plate 5, are the Finance Control Office, the BICEC office (all of which still exist today), Relais Hotel (presently an off-Licence), SGBC (presently used as a Law Chambers) and Credit Lyonnaise (occupied by the Delegation of Social Affairs). Also, Companies like Tsekenis, Vlandis, Jalem, Herekigui, Continal, K.W. King, CFAO, SIRCO, PANAFRIC, Javeny, and Chococam, closed down their activities/shops in Nkongsamba. Plate 6 shows the abandoned Chococam building which is presently used by a glass manufacturer.

Plate 6: Former Chococam Factory and Retail Structure (ground floor)
Source: Field work, (January, 2010)

Out of seven petrol stations that existed in Nkongsamba in 1960, and between 1970 and 1984, only 3 of them now exist. Petrol stations like SCDP, Mobil, and Agip no longer exist in Nkongsamba. The two Mobil stations have been converted into bus stations and one used by the Central Voyage and the other by Stella Voyage. Furthermore, the vehicle sales point that existed in Nkongsamba between 1960s and 1984 like SOCADA (SCOA), CAMI TOYOTA and RENAULT has all relocated to Bafoussam and Doula where there is a ready market. Summarily, the previous and present status of some activities in Nkongsamba is explained in Table 2.

Table 2: Current status of major activities in Nkongsamba

Activity	Location in Nkongsamba	Present Status/2024	Cause
Car rentals/sales point	Central Business District	Relocated to Bafoussam	Low profit
Clothing companies like Vlandis, Tsekenis.	Central Business District	Relocated to Melong, Douala and Bafoussam	Reduction in the demand of their commodities
Transport Companies like La Chanas	Central Business District	Relocated to Ngaoundere	Closure of the railway line
Other establishments like PANAFRIC, CFAO, SIRCO, & CHOCOCAM	Central Business District	Relocated to Douala and Bafoussam	Low profits

Source: Field Data (2010/2024)

Other infrastructures like hotels that were constructed to accommodate visitors and businessmen during the growth period are now dilapidated with no indications of renovation. Hotels like the Hotel du Mungo (a three star hotel) which was the best during the 1960s to 1980s in terms of structure, number of rooms, and facilities offered, can currently be rated among the least (a one star hotel) not because others have emerged to compete with it but because of the fall in the economy which does not make it profitable even after renovation. In addition, the Guinness depot in Nkongsamba which was the largest in the Mungo Division had been relocated to Melong as a result of the reduction in sales of its products. Plate 7 shows the abandoned Guinness depot of Nkongsamba. Its dilapidated outlook has affected the aesthetics of the Town considering its location in the centre of the Town.

Plate 7: An abandoned Guinness Depot in Nkongsamba
Source: Field work, (December, 2009)

Decline in Health facilities

Following the growth of Nkongsamba between the 1960s and 1990s in terms of immigration and natural increase, there was a need for an improvement in the health sector. Private clinics and Hospitals were constructed, as well as the construction of the present Government Regional Hospital. These helped to cater for the health needs of the growing population. However, with the decline in economic activities, most of the private clinics have closed down, including a private mortuary. According to Field data (2009), the natives for example resorted to non-scientific methods to embalm the dead rather than using the mortuary because of poverty. Plate 8 illustrates an abandoned private clinic which could not operate below its running costs probably due to the declining population and declining socio-economic activities of the Town.

Plate 8: An abandoned Private clinic in Nkongsamba
Source: Field work, (February, 2010)

Decline in Educational Infrastructures

Given the decline in the socio-economic activities of Nkongsamba, the educational sector also faced some problems in terms of maintenance of the infrastructures and total number of students enrolled in various institutions. According to Field data (2010), an institution like College Moderne du Nkongsamba (present day Lycee de Manengouba), formerly accommodated students from neighbouring countries and regions and was entirely controlled by foreigners. Also, considering its former status as the 2nd after Lycee Leclerk in Yaounde in the 1980s, the institution's role today has dropped. It is now facing a serious problem of infrastructural degradation and maintenance. The dormitory section is no more in existence as the structures are no longer habitable. Other higher institution like the Socka Bongue Institute that was created to train students on development is no longer in existence and have been converted into a secondary institution.

Socio-political events

Before Cameroon gained its independence in 1960, the country was controlled and managed by the French as a colony. In 1950, an opposition party named the "Union des Population du Cameroon" (UPC) was created in Nkongsamba by Moumé Etia, instigated

ISSN 2709-3409 (Online)

by a member of the French Communist Party to give Cameroon an unconditional independence. This was to be a form of compensation after the Cameroonians helped them in the First and Second World War.

In 1955, the UPC party started a rebellion campaign against the French in Douala where many of them were shot dead by the French forces. In retaliation, the party members relocated in Nkongsamba where they started kidnapping the French farmers who were owners of some agricultural firms (constituted coffee farms, poultry farms and the rearing of animals) in the Town. It should be recalled that, the agricultural firms during this period were controlled entirely by foreigners since they had the financial capital to manage the estates. From the kidnapping of these farmers, huge ransoms were being paid for their release. The kidnapping of these farmers scared them and obliged some of them to sell their estates that were located in the outskirts of the Town of Nkongsamba to Cameroonians and only concentrated on their processing mills located within the Town for safety reasons. The irony here is that, these farms that were being sold were bought by prominent UPC members, giving a clear understanding that the money was obtained from the "kidnapping business" of the UPC. According to Field data (2010), the largest firm was bought by M. Thimothé Yemou, the then treasurer of the UPC, while the best hotel in the whole of Mungo (Hotel du Mongo) at the time, was owned by M. Tchouafé, another member of the party. Other firms were bought by members like Mr. Ernest Wandji, the army leader of the party and Dr. Felix Moumé who was the first president of the party.

It should be noted here that politics had nothing to do with the international price of coffee, but played a role in the management of the agricultural firms. One of such roles was witnessed by mismanagement of the firms, the retrenchment of workers to reduce expenses as well as the reduction of workers' salaries. Thus, as the foreigners left, their income-generating ventures also dwindled. All of these have contributed to the decline in the economy of Nkongsamba, as well as the reduction of some investments that could have emanated therefrom.

Discussion

The Town of Nkongsamba remains a potential agricultural melting pot due to its rich volcanic and mountain climate that encourages cash crop production. The French Agricultural Policy of massive exploitation in the 20th Century contributed enormously to the growth of the Town within this period. Findings on the agricultural economy of Nkongsamba ties to its coffee economy, which reveal a sector of major concern that has triggered the growth and development of the Town and should be considered with much concern for the local government of the area and urban development planners in general. Arias (2010) argued that agriculture plays a significant role in encouraging urbanisation and sustainable development of a place. Paz et al. (2009) added that higher agricultural value means more income is generated to ameliorate poverty levels of farmers and related farming activities. This as well coincides with the findings that farmers were better off with high cost of coffee and the standard dropped when coffee prices dropped at the world market.

Johnston et al. (1961) in their work on the role of agriculture in economic development explained that, not only does agriculture fuel economic growth through the provision of food and the necessity for unskilled labour, but it also supplies capital and labour to other industrial sectors. They added that, such activities can also serve as a market for industrial output and innovation. This falls in line with one of the research findings of migrants into Nkongsamba soliciting for both skilled and unskilled jobs. Also, in serving as a market for industrial output, the different cloth industries, cars, transportation industries, all came into Nkongsamba due to the benefits derived from the growing agricultural economy.

Based on challenges faced, the drop in world coffee prices saw the collapse of the economy, making the Town to remain a pale reflection of what it used to be. Erol et al. (2011) in this line of thought attest that global economic crisis leading to a drop in world prices of products, including agricultural products, now questions the absolute role of agriculture in sustainable development and poverty alleviation.

Recommendations and Best Urban Practice

In order for the Town of Nkongsamba to gain its status as an urban centre and an administrative capital for which it is, the following recommendations based on research have been posited.

Based on the Agricultural Economy:

1. Diversification of agricultural production should be encouraged. Since coffee no longer has the commanding status it used to have, food crops such as beans, maize, cocoyams, and fruits which are being cultivated at smaller scales, can be revitalized for commercial purposes since they have a ready demand in the local, national and international markets.
2. The government of Cameroon could encourage businessmen to invest in the construction of processing plants for the farm produce to be consumed locally since some farmers still prefer cultivating coffee.
3. Cooperatives should be created so that farmers can be able to have incentives and contract loans at cheaper interest rates. This can help enhance productivity and investment in the agricultural sector.
4. Organizations like the defunct National Produce Marketing Board (N.P.M.B.), can be put in place to help regulate world agricultural prices for the benefit of the farmers. It should be noted that the collapse of the N.P.M.B. was due to the allocation of its funds for payment of civil servants nationwide.

Based on the Transportation Sector;

1. Rehabilitation of the railway sector is imperative in order to enable goods to be transported to various demanding areas, and other goods needed in Nkongsamba.
2. The major roads connecting the streets should be rehabilitated. Though some of the roads have been rehabilitated between 2015 and 2022, much is still desired from the councils especially the farm to market roads.

Generally, some measures to improve the development of the Town include;

1. Industrialization in its various dimensions in order to create jobs and encourage the attraction of other commercial activities like banks, microfinance, as well as potential investors.
2. There is a need for a collective conscience between the natives of Nkongsamba and the migrants. Creating a peaceful and friendly atmosphere with the migrant community will definitely encourage the migrants to invest in that locality without fear of threats from the land owners in the future.
3. In the absence of the coffee or agricultural sector, a more lucrative and productive sector like the tourism sector can be encouraged. In creating structures like a museum, artefacts and other sculptures which may include among others the former colonial or prominent figures in the history and paintings from renowned artist who are natives, can make meaningful contributions to growth. This will attract tourists from around the nation and abroad, thereby changing the Town from an agricultural to a sustainable ecotouristic environment.
4. Planning techniques like the construction of “green sites”, as well as recreational sites within the inner city is imperative for the health, sanitation and aesthetics of the Town.
5. It is also necessary for the municipal council to constantly update its Master Plan to help guide development and development control to the next short and long-run periods. This will help in updating the government on the dynamic nature of the urban environment in terms of residential demands and population growth.
6. The Mungo Division can be mapped out to constitute a region with Nkongsamba being the regional capital. This will encourage the development of socio-economic activities like the creation of health centres, markets, among others.

In order for the above recommendations to be implemented, a proper planning and organizational body need to be put in place to comprise the City Council, administration and notables to strictly follow the implementation process.

4 Conclusion

The world over, cities are known to be centres of attraction to both the rural migrants and investors due to the services offered within these cities. It is therefore imperative for our major cities to continue playing their role as such without losing sight of the implications of growth and decline. Within the African context, most of our cities today were colonial, most of which have developed to become growth poles and growth centres. Most of the cities have grown as a result of the industrialization process and other investments brought in by the colonial masters. The present problems of Nkongsamba can best be attributed to the fact that all its resources were orientated towards the coffee economy, without any forecast in the trend of coffee prices. Though introduced by the colonial masters, a corresponding interest in terms of developing other sectors of the economy was imperative. Since the whole economy of the Town was dependent on the coffee

ISSN 2709-3409 (Online)

business, the entire Town was forced to decline as the coffee economy experienced a sustained drop in prices.

However, if some of the above recommendations can be put in to place, a sustainable urban environment can be achieved in which other sectors of the economy can best contribute to the creation of jobs, and improvement in income levels of the urban dwellers. According to Fombe (2005), the realization of a sustainable and liveable city requires both an integrated planning and decision-making framework, and a fundamental shift from traditional values and perspectives. The problem of Nkongsamba is considered as a unique situation where an administrative centre which was formerly ranked as third after Douala and Yaoundé in the 1970's is presently under conditions of stagnation and increasing urban poverty. This is a call for concern as the need for urban rehabilitation becomes eminent.

5 References

- Arias, J. (2010). The contribution of agriculture to sustainable development in Jamaica. San Jose, Costa Rica: IICA. Retrieved from <https://goo.gl/yGQJdY>, 16.03.2024
- Breeze, G. (ed.) (1972). The city in newly developing countries. Readings on Urbanism and Urbanization, Prentice Hall, International Inc., London
- Christiaensen, L., Demery, L., and Kuhl, J. (2011). The evolving role of agriculture in Poverty reduction - An Empirical Perspective, *Journal of Development Economics*, 96 (2), 239-254
- Drakakis-Smith, D. (2000), *3rd world cities* (2nd edition), Routledge, London.
- Erol, M., Apak, S., Atmaca, M., and Öztürk, S. (2011). Management measures to be taken for the enterprise in difficulty during times of global crisis: an Empirical study. *Procedia - Social and Behavioural Sciences*, Vol. 24, 2011, pp. 16-32
- Fombe, L.F. (2005): Sub-Standard Housing and Slum Development in Douala: An Urban Development Perspective. Unpublished PhD Thesis, University of Buea.
- Gilbert, A and Gugler, J. (1981) *Cities, poverty and development: Urbanization in the 3rd world*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK.
- Gilbert, A., and Gugler, J. (1981) *Cities, poverty and development: Urbanization in the 3rd world*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, UK.
- Hoselitz, B. F. (1953). The Role of Cities in the Economic Growth of Underdeveloped Countries. *Journal of Political Economy*, 61 (3), 195-208
- Johnston, B. F., and Mellor, J. W. (1961). The role of agriculture in economic development. *The American Economic Review*, 51(4), 566-593
- Land Tenure and Property Rights, id21, No. 48, October 2003.
- Mabogunje, A. L. (1986). *Urbanisation in Nigeria*, University of London, London
- National Institute of Statistics (2005, 2010 est). *Population and Housing Census of Cameroon, Projections and Archives*, Ministry of Scientific Research, Cameroon

ISSN 2709-3409 (Online)

- Nawagamuwa, A. and Viking N. (2003) *Urban Sustainability in Developing Contexts*, Royal Institute of Technology, Stockholm, Sweden
- Neba, A. (1999): Modern Geography of the Republic of Cameroon, 3rd Edition, Neba Publishers, Bamenda.
- Paz, J., Benavides, H., and Arias, J. (2009). Measuring agricultural GDP Performance: A Technical Note. COMUNIICA. Retrieved from <http://goo.gl/TrPFmd>, 18.03.2004
- Rapport du Commune d’Nkongsamba (1970). *Urbanisme dans la ville métropolitaine de Nkongsamba*, Littoral Province, Cameroun
- The World Bank (2003): *World Development Report 2003, Sustainable Development in the Developing World*, Oxford University Press, New York.
- World Bank Group. (2015). *Enabling the business of agriculture*. Washington DC: World Bank Group